

Descending Retropharyngeal abscess: Report of A Case

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ABSTRACT

Retropharyngeal abscess is a dangerous condition affecting patients presenting to emergency room. The etiology is a bacterial in most instances. The swelling can affect the airway and be a life threatening condition. Immediate recognition, attention and intervention are essential to practitioners of medicine. This case illustrates a patient who presented with acute respiratory distress to emergency room. The condition had worsened and extended down to laryngeal space.

Keywords: Retropharyngeal abscess; Bacteria; Respiratory

INTRODUCTION

Retropharyngeal abscess is a condition that usually starts with infection of lymph nodes. This is a collection of pus that extends either from contiguous area or the space is directly inoculated.^[1] The infection usually starts as an infection in tonsil, sinuses, adenoids or nose. Iatrogenic causes such as laryngoscopy, endoscopy, intubation, tube feed insertion, head and neck surgery or dental procedures (i.e. dental injections) could also contribute to this problem. This type of presentation usually begins in lymph nodes at the back of the pharynx and it presents more commonly in children between 1 to 8 years old. The incidence of these cases decreases as the age increases.^[2] This type of infection is usually oral flora although the cultures usually grow mixed flora. It is common to have some traumatic injury that leads to inoculation of the pharynx (i.e. Fish bone). Risk factors include immune dysfunction in patients with HIV, diabetes, or poor oral hygiene.

The main symptoms are pain and swelling of the throat, fever and enlarged cervical lymph nodes.^[3,4] Patients are usually start with sensation of cold and sore throat however the symptoms continue to progress to a point where the airway starts to close. This is the usual point of presentation to emergency room. Voice changes and drooling is common. In severe cases the neck may be stiff and patients may hold their head at an angle.

This condition if untreated is associated with severe complications. The first possibility is ruptured abscess and flow of pus into the lungs leading to pneumonia. Vocal cord irritation could lead to spasm and difficulty breathing.

Severe infections could extend to Jugular veins and lead to clot formation or to Carotid artery with catastrophic rupture of the vessels. One of the most severe complications is extension of the infection in the retropharyngeal space down to chest and heart. Purulent pericarditis, tamponade, pyopneumothorax, pleuritis, empyema or bronchial erosion are some of the pleural complications. At times necrotizing fasciitis or Septic shock again could be a final presenting sign of these patients.

Understanding of fascial planes of the neck is important to treating clinicians. Superficial and deep fascia are usually present in the neck and although they are adherent with no gap there is potential space that can be separated and purulent cavity formed. The retropharyngeal space is located posterior to pharynx. This includes the Nasopharynx, oropharynx and hypopharynx. The anterior border of this space is the buccopharyngeal fascia surrounds the trachea, esophagus, and thyroid. The carotid sheaths and the parapharyngeal space form the lateral portions. Finally, posteriorly it is the prevertebral fascia that faces this space. The superior border extends to base of skull and inferiorly it extends to mediastinum at level of bifurcation of the trachea. There are two potential spaces posterior to retropharyngeal space. The Danger space and Prevertebral space extend down to diaphragm. These spaces give potential for rapid growing abscess to extend to mediastinum leading to fatal mediastinitis.

The cultures usually are polymicrobial. The most common bacteria are aerobic gram positive bacteria but over time may graduate to gram negative anaerobic bacteria. Studies have shown that Methicillin resistance Staphylococcus infection is increasing.^[3] The incidence of Mycobacterium tuberculosis, Bartonella Henselae and Coccidioides is increased in immunosuppressed individuals.

REPORT OF CASE

A 65-year-old Asian male presented to emergency room for evaluation of pain upon swallowing. He reported 3-day history of sore throat that is acutely worsening. The problem had started with a fish bone lodging the day either prior to start of symptoms. At the time of presentation, patient had difficulty swallowing his saliva and had fever. The presenting signs also included tachycardia at 95 and fever of 100^oF. Clinical exam revealed a large swelling of the submandibular and left lateral neck with lymphadenopathy of bilateral cervical lymph nodes. Intra oral examination revealed red and swollen left tonsillar pillars and deviation of uvula. The left and posterior walls of pharynx were swollen (Figure 1). Patient had spasm on intra oral examination. Computer Tomography was obtained (Figure 2) which revealed retropharyngeal purulence extending to vocal cords. Patient was taken immediately to operating room and intraoral approach using sedation anesthesia and topical application were carried out. Tracheostomy instruments were available in case of airway emergency. Incision and drainage of the area and antibiotic irrigation was obtained and cultures were sent for evaluation.

The patient gradually improved with intravenous antibiotics and on third postoperative day was discharged with oral antibiotics.

Figure 1: Patient presentation with a retro and parapharyngeal space infection

Figure 2: Patient with retropharyngeal space infection.

DISCUSSION

Studies have been carried on pediatric group to assess the incidence of retropharyngeal abscess in children to be 2.6 percent.^[5] Other studies released in 2014 revealed that the incidence had increased between 2000 to 2009.^[6] The infection however had shorter hospital course. It has been shown that there is a correlation between the incidence of infection and lower socioeconomic status.^[7] This is mostly contributed by reduced accessibility to health care combined with poor oral hygiene. It has been shown that retropharyngeal abscess is almost exclusively a pediatric diagnosis.^[8,9,10] The children under age of 6 usually have retropharyngeal nodes that are in process of atrophy and fibrosis. The upper respiratory infection however could lead to cellulitis and enlargement of these lymph nodes and subsequent spread to the retropharyngeal tissues. The peritonsillar abscess is more common in older individuals. The possibility of spread is low since the nodes in the retropharyngeal space are mostly fibrosed. There is no difference in male to female incidence however there are studies that favor boys.^[8] There are also no racial differences noticed in previous studies.

The prognosis of the patients with normal health is excellent. In severe cases, it is essential to keep the patient in acute care facility and access the airway by a specialist. No sedations should be provided until patient is in controlled conditions. General anesthesia with intubation should be with direct visualization or surgical access using tracheostomy.^[11] In severe cases, these infections could extend to Carotid artery leading to rupture with 20-40% mortality and lead to Jugular vein thrombosis with 60% mortality.^[12,13] Correct diagnosis and immediate treatment could make a significant difference in morbidity and mortality of the patients.

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